

STABILITY INDICATING UV SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF CAFFEINE AND SODIUM BENZOATE

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ABSTRACT

Sodium benzoate and caffeine are commonly used preservatives and stimulants in carbonated beverages. Their levels must be monitored to ensure compliance with regulatory limits and assess potential health risks. This study aimed to develop and validate a cost-effective UV-spectrophotometric methods for quantifying sodium benzoate and caffeine in commercial soft drinks. The quantification was based on maximum absorption at wavelengths of 224 nm and 272 nm, respectively, using water as the solvent system. Two technique was developed, and method was demonstrated with excellent linearity ($R^2 = 0.998$), precision (%RSD < 2%), and accuracy (% recovery: 97.78%). The LOD and LOQ for sodium benzoate were found to be 0.3552 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 1.0763 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, while for caffeine, they were 0.3481 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 1.0548 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, respectively.

Forced degradation studies were conducted under five stress conditions (acidic, alkaline, oxidative, thermal, and photolytic). The highest degradation was observed under photolytic conditions (98.92% for sodium benzoate, 85.34% for caffeine), indicating the importance of controlled storage conditions. Analysis of commercial soft drinks revealed sodium benzoate concentrations between 5.7062–8.8184 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and caffeine concentrations between 27.6953–30.6262 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The detected levels were within the FDA-approved limits (0.1% w/w for sodium benzoate, up to 300 mg/L for caffeine).

The validated method is reliable for routine quality control of sodium benzoate and caffeine in beverages. The findings emphasize the need for stringent quality control measures to ensure consumer safety and product stability.

Sodium benzoate and caffeine are widely used as preservatives and stimulants in carbonated beverages, necessitating their routine monitoring to ensure regulatory compliance and assess potential health risks. This study aimed to develop and validate a cost-effective UV-spectrophotometric method for the quantification of sodium benzoate and caffeine in

commercial soft drinks. The quantification was performed at maximum absorption wavelengths of 224 nm for sodium benzoate and 272 nm for caffeine, using water as the solvent system. Two analytical techniques were developed, and the method demonstrated excellent linearity ($R^2 = 0.998$), precision (%RSD < 2%), and accuracy (% recovery: 97.78%). The limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ) for sodium benzoate were determined to be 0.3552 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 1.0763 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, respectively, while for caffeine, they were 0.3481 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 1.0548 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

To evaluate the stability of the analytes, forced degradation studies were conducted under five stress conditions: acidic, alkaline, oxidative, thermal, and photolytic. The highest degradation was observed under photolytic conditions, with degradation rates of 98.92% for sodium benzoate and 85.34% for caffeine, underscoring the importance of proper storage conditions to maintain product stability. Analysis of commercially available soft drinks revealed sodium benzoate concentrations ranging from 5.7062 to 8.8184 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and caffeine concentrations between 27.6953 and 30.6262 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, all within FDA-approved limits (0.1% w/w for sodium benzoate and up to 300 mg/L for caffeine).

The validated method provides a reliable, accurate, and cost-effective approach for routine quality control of sodium benzoate and caffeine in carbonated beverages. The findings highlight the necessity for stringent quality control measures to ensure product safety, regulatory compliance, and consumer protection. Given the widespread consumption of these beverages, this study holds significant relevance for regulatory agencies, manufacturers, and public health authorities, reinforcing the importance of continuous monitoring to uphold food safety standards

Keywords: Sodium benzoate, caffeine, UV-spectrophotometry, forced degradation, method validation, soft drinks.

1.INTRODUCTION¹⁻⁶

Spectrophotometric analysis is one of the most widely utilized techniques for analyzing compounds in simple and complex mixtures. The advancement of spectrophotometer software has enabled multicomponent analysis, making it a powerful tool in fields such as clinical chemistry, pharmaceuticals, food analysis, and environmental monitoring. UV-Vis spectrophotometry, in particular, is valued for its speed, simplicity, and cost-effectiveness, making it indispensable for ensuring food quality and safety. This technique is extensively

employed in the food and beverage industry for analyzing additives such as caffeine and sodium benzoate, which are commonly used as stimulants and preservatives.

Caffeine, chemically known as 1,3,7-trimethylxanthine ($C_8H_{10}N_4O_2$), is a widely consumed stimulant found in various beverages and foods. It enhances brain activity by acting as an adenosine antagonist, making it a popular ingredient in energy drinks, soft drinks, and medicines. Pure caffeine is an odorless, bitter-tasting white powder with a molecular weight of 194.19 g/mol and moderate water solubility (21.7 g/L). Regulatory agencies, such as the U.S. FDA, impose limits on caffeine content in beverages to mitigate potential health risks, restricting its concentration to 30–72 mg per 335 mL.

Sodium benzoate ($C_7H_5NaO_2$), a widely used preservative, is the sodium salt of benzoic acid. It prevents microbial growth and is frequently added to soft drinks, bread, sauces, and other processed foods. While effective in prolonging shelf life, sodium benzoate can cause allergic reactions such as urticaria and asthma when consumed in excessive amounts. Regulatory authorities, including the FDA and European agencies, have set limits on its use, typically capped at 0.1% or 200–2000 mg/L, depending on the product.

The simultaneous quantification of caffeine and sodium benzoate in beverages is essential for maintaining food quality, ensuring regulatory compliance, and safeguarding public health. However, the concurrent analysis of these compounds remains a challenge due to the need for precise, efficient, and cost-effective analytical methods.

This study aims to address this challenge by developing and validating a UV-Vis spectrophotometric method for the simultaneous estimation of caffeine and sodium benzoate. The method will be designed to be simple, rapid, and precise, suitable for routine analysis in the food and beverage industry. Additionally, the stability of these compounds under various stress conditions—such as acidic, alkaline, oxidative, thermal, and photolytic degradation—will be assessed to evaluate their behavior during processing and storage.

The outcomes of this study will contribute to the advancement of analytical techniques, enabling better quality control and regulatory compliance while ensuring consumer safety. By employing methods such as Vierordt's method, absorbance ratio (Q-absorbance) method, and dual wavelength analysis, this research provides a comprehensive approach to addressing the analytical needs of the food and beverage sector.

2.MATERIALS AND METHODS

Reagents and chemicals.

Sodium Benzoate and Caffeine extra pure 98% (analytical standard, batch no: 7216784, MFG date: 03/2023) is purchased from SISCO Research Laboratories PVT Ltd Maharashtra Various brands of marketed carbonated soft drinks and fruit juice were purchased locally from the market..0.1 N Sodium hydroxide and Hydrochloric acid 3% Hydrogen peroxide and Distilled water were used in the studies

Instrument

The Systronics Spectrophotometer 2202 is a UV/Visible double-beam spectrophotometer featuring a spectral bandwidth of 2 nm and a wavelength resolution of 0.5 nm. All spectral measurements were conducted using a set of 1 cm matched quartz cells. Shimadzu digital weighing balance and Heating mantle was used

Parameter fixations

Final solvent system selected for the study was found to be distilled water.Sodium benzoate and Caffeine was found to be 224nm and 272nm respectively. Hence the 200-400 nm range is fixed for the analysis.

Preparation of Standard Stock Solution

A standard stock solution of sodium benzoate was prepared by accurately weighing 0.1 g and dissolving it in a 10 mL standard flask with distilled water. From this primary stock solution, 2.5 mL was pipetted into a 25 mL standard flask and diluted to volume with distilled water to obtain the secondary stock solution. Similarly, a standard stock solution of caffeine was prepared by weighing 0.1 g and dissolving it in 10 mL of distilled water. A 2.5 mL aliquot of this primary stock solution was then transferred to a 25 mL standard flask and diluted to volume with distilled water to obtain the secondary stock solution.

Calibration Curve of Sodium Benzoate and Caffeine

For the calibration curve, aliquots of 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2, 2.5, and 3 mL from the secondary stock solutions were pipetted and diluted to 10 mL, yielding final concentrations of 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, and 30 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of sodium benzoate and caffeine. The absorbance of these solutions was measured in the 200–400 nm range, and a calibration curve was plotted between absorbance and concentration

Preparation of Marketed sample solution

A sample solution was prepared by pipetting 1 mL of PRD, 1.03 mL of STN, 1.03 mL of CG, and 2.31 mL of MD into a 10 mL standard flask and diluting to volume with distilled water, resulting in a final concentration of 30 µg/mL. The absorbance of the resulting solution was measured at 224 nm and 272 nm, and the concentrations of sodium benzoate and caffeine were determined.

Technique 1: Vierordt's Method⁷⁻¹⁰

This method is based on the absorption of drugs sodium benzoate and caffeine at their wavelength maxima's. The two-wavelength selected for the development of simultaneous equation are 224 nm and 272 nm. The absorptivity values are determined. The concentrations of Sodium Benzoate (C_x) and Caffeine (C_y) were calculated using the following equations:

$$C_x = \frac{A_2 a_{y1} - A_1 a_{y2}}{a_{x2} a_{y1} - a_{x1} a_{y2}}$$

$$C_y = \frac{A_1 a_{x2} - A_2 a_{x1}}{a_{x2} a_{y1} - a_{x1} a_{y2}}$$

Where A_1 and A_2 are the absorbances at 224 nm and 272 nm, respectively; a_{x1} , a_{x2} , a_{y1} and a_{y2} are the absorptivity's of Sodium Benzoate (C_x) and Caffeine (C_y) at these wavelengths.

Technique 2: Absorbance ratio method¹¹⁻¹⁵

(Q-Absorbance method)

This method is based on the absorbance at two selected wavelength one is an isobestic point and other being the wavelength of maxima absorption of one of the components. From the overlay spectra 224 nm selected as the isobestic point and 272 nm (λ max of caffeine) is selected for Q- absorption ratio method. The absorptivity values determined for sodium benzoate and caffeine at 224 nm and 272 nm respectively. These values are substituted in the following equation

$$C_x = \frac{Q_M - Q_Y}{Q_X - Q_Y} \times \frac{A_1}{a_{x1}}$$

$$C_y = \frac{Q_M - Q_X}{Q_Y - Q_X} \times \frac{A_1}{a_{y1}}$$

$$Q_M = \frac{A_2}{A_1} \quad Q_X = \frac{a_{x2}}{a_{x1}} \quad Q_Y = \frac{a_{y2}}{a_{y1}}$$

Where, C_x is the concentration of Sodium Benzoate (C_x) and C_y concentration of Caffeine, A_1 & A_2 are the absorbance of the mixture at λ_1 nm (224 nm isobestic point) & λ_2 nm (272 nm)

respectively; a_{x1} and a_{y1} are absorptivity of Sodium Benzoate (C_x) and Caffeine (C_y) at λ_1 nm ; a_{x2} and a_{y2} are absorptivity of Sodium Benzoate (C_x) and Caffeine (C_y) at λ_2 nm.

Fig 1: overlay spectrum

Forced Degradation Studies¹⁶⁻²⁰

Preparation of Standard solution

0.1g of sodium benzoate and caffeine was accurately weighed and transferred into separate 10 mL standard flasks, then diluted to volume with distilled water to prepare the primary stock solution. From this, 2.5 mL was pipetted into a 25 mL standard flask and diluted to volume with distilled water to obtain the secondary stock solution. Finally, 3 mL of the secondary stock solution was transferred into a 10 mL standard flask and diluted to the mark with distilled water to prepare the standard solution.

Acid and Alkaline degradation

For acid and alkaline degradation studies, 3 mL of the standard solution of sodium benzoate and caffeine was transferred into separate 10 mL standard flasks. For acid degradation, 3 mL of 0.1N HCl was added, while for alkaline degradation, 3 mL of 0.1N NaOH was added. Both solutions were refluxed for 15 minutes and kept in the dark. After cooling, the volume was made up with distilled water, and absorbance was measured using UV spectroscopy.

Thermal and Oxidative degradation

For thermal and oxidative degradation studies, 3 mL of the standard solution of sodium benzoate and caffeine was transferred into separate 10 mL standard flasks. For thermal degradation, the solutions were made up to volume with distilled water and heated at 40°C for 5 minutes. For oxidative degradation, 1 mL of 6% w/v H₂O₂ was added, and the solution

was kept in the dark for 15 minutes before making up the volume with distilled water. Absorbance was then measured using UV spectroscopy.

Photolytic degradation

Transfer 3ml of standard solution of Sodium benzoate and caffeine into two separate 10ml standard flask and kept in sunlight for 24Hrs. The absorbance is measured using UV spectroscopy.

METHOD VALIDATION²¹⁻³⁵

The proposed method was validated for the parameters like linearity, precision, accuracy, robustness, ruggedness, limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantization (LOQ) as per ICH guidelines

Linearity

The linearity was determined by using the solution of concentration between 5.0 - 30 μ g/ml. Absorbance of the solutions was found and plotted a graph between absorbance and concentration of the solution using Microsoft Excel. And also found the correlation coefficient and regression equation.

Precision

Precision was assessed by intraday, interday/ruggedness, reproducibility studies. 5.0, 10.0, and 15.0 μ g/ml Sodium benzoate and caffeine solution was analyzed thrice in a day for intraday studies and %RSD was found. In interday 5.0, 10.0, and 15.0 μ g/ml Sodium benzoate and caffeine solution was analyzed in three successive days and %RSD was calculated. For repeatability study 10.0 μ g/ml of Sodium benzoate and caffeine solution was analyzed for 6 times.

Accuracy

The accuracy for the analytical method was evaluated at 80, 100 & 120 % levels of 10.0 μ g/ml standard solution. Absorbance was measured in wavelength range 200-400 nm and results were obtained in terms of percent recovery. Then %RSD was calculated.

Robustness

It is measure of its capacity to remain unaffected by small, but deliberate variation in method or parameter and provide a indication of its reliability on storage.

Robustness is measured by taking absorbance of 15.0 μ g/ml of solution Sodium benzoate and Caffeine by slight variation in wavelength 224 \pm 1.0 and 272 \pm 1.0 nm respectively.

Limit of Detection (LOD)

The **LOD** is the lowest concentration of an analyte that can be detected but not necessarily quantified. It was calculated using the formula:

LOD = $3.3\sigma / S$, where σ is the standard deviation of the response and **S** is the slope of the regression equation.

Absorbance values for 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, and 30 μ g/mL solutions of sodium benzoate and caffeine were recorded, and the LOD was determined as:

- **Sodium benzoate:** 0.3552 μ g/mL
- **Caffeine:** 0.3481 μ g/mL

Limit of Quantification (LOQ)

The **LOQ** is the lowest concentration of an analyte that can be accurately quantified. It was determined using the formula:

LOQ = $10\sigma / S$, where σ is the standard deviation of the response and **S** is the slope of the regression equation.

Using the same absorbance data, the LOQ was calculated as:

- **Sodium benzoate:** 1.0763 μ g/mL
- **Caffeine:** 1.0548 μ g/mL

4.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

UV Spectral Analysis

The absorption maxima (λ_{max}) of sodium benzoate and caffeine were found to be **224 nm and 272 nm**, respectively. These wavelengths were selected for further analysis as they exhibited **maximum absorbance with minimal interference** from other components in the sample matrix.

Linearity and Calibration Curve

The method demonstrated excellent **linearity** over the concentration range of **5–30 µg/mL** for both sodium benzoate and caffeine. The **correlation coefficient ($R^2 = 0.998$)** confirmed a strong linear relationship between **absorbance and concentration**, indicating the suitability of the method for quantitative analysis. The regression equation obtained further supports the reliability of the method for accurate quantification.

Fig 2: calibration curve of sodium benzoate

Fig 3: Calibration curve of Caffeine

Precision Study

The precision of the method was evaluated through **intraday, interday (ruggedness), and repeatability** studies. The results indicated that the **%RSD values for all precision parameters were below 2%**, demonstrating minimal variation between repeated measurements. This confirms that the method is highly **reproducible and reliable** for routine analysis.

Table 1: Precision study of Sodium Benzoate and Caffeine

Precision	Conc (µg/ml)	Absorbance		Mean absorbance		SD		% RSD	
		Sodium Benzoate	Caffeine						
Intra day	5	0.540	0.529	0.5416	0.532	0.0015	0.0026	0.2820	0.4973
		0.542	0.533						
		0.543	0.534						
	10	0.728	0.723	0.7303	0.725	0.0025	0.002	0.3445	0.2758
		0.730	0.725						
		0.733	0.727						
	15	0.931	0.919	0.934	0.9216	0.0036	0.0030	0.3860	0.3314
		0.933	0.921						
		0.938	0.925						
Inter day/	5	0.542	0.530	0.5353	0.535	0.0058	0.0062	1.0945	1.1672
		0.533	0.533						
		0.531	0.542						
	10	0.730	0.735	0.7216	0.7296	0.0076	0.0050	1.0583	0.6897
		0.720	0.725						
		0.715	0.729						
			0.931	0.932	0.920	0.920	0.0100	0.0115	1.087

rugge dness	15	0.920	0.921	6	6			9	
		0.911	0.909						
Repe atabil ity	10	0.730	0.723	0.726 3	0.728 3	0.0085	0.0063	1.183 2	0.8669
		0.728	0.725						
		0.741	0.739						
		0.718	0.733						
		0.721	0.724						
		0.720	0.726						

Accuracy and Recovery Studies

The accuracy of the developed method was assessed through **recovery studies at three concentration levels (80%, 100%, and 120%)**. The percent recovery was found to be within the range of **97.78%**, with **%RSD values between 0.5102 and 1.1056**. These results indicate that the method provides **accurate and precise quantification** of sodium benzoate and caffeine in pharmaceutical formulations.

Table 2: Recovery study

Accuracy Level	Std Conc. (µg/ml)	Amt Added (µg/ml)	Mean % Recovery (Caffeine) ± SD (% RSD)	Mean % Recovery (Sodium Benzoate) ± SD (% RSD)
80%	10	8	96.96 ± 1.06 (1.09)	97.66 ± 0.20 (0.21)
100%	10	10	97.65 ± 0.50 (0.51)	98.39 ± 1.06 (1.08)
120%	10	12	98.78 ± 1.09 (1.11)	98.80 ± 0.61 (0.62)

Average mean determination three in each level

Robustness

Robustness was evaluated by introducing deliberate variations in analytical conditions, specifically by altering the detection wavelength (224 ± 1 nm for sodium benzoate and 272 ± 1 nm for caffeine). The observed %RSD values of 0.1640% and 0.2869% confirmed that slight variations in method parameters did not significantly impact the results. This establishes the method as robust and reliable for routine laboratory applications.

Table 3: Robustness study

Si. no	Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Wave length Deviation	Wave length (nm)	Absorbance (Sodium Benzoate)	Mean (Sodium Benzoate)	% RSD (Sodium Benzoate)	Absorbance (Caffeine)	Mean (Caffeine)	% RSD (Caffeine)
1	15	-1	223.0 / 271.0	0.93	0.9313	0.164	0.92	0.922	0.2869
2	15	0	224.0 / 272.0	0.931			0.921		
3	15	1	225.0 / 273.0	0.933			0.925		

Sensitivity: Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ)

The LOD and LOQ were calculated to assess the method's sensitivity. The LOD values were found to be $0.3552 \mu\text{g/mL}$ for sodium benzoate and $0.3481 \mu\text{g/mL}$ for caffeine, indicating the lowest concentration detectable by the method. The LOQ values were determined as $1.0763 \mu\text{g/mL}$ for sodium benzoate and $1.0548 \mu\text{g/mL}$ for caffeine, confirming the method's capability to accurately quantify low concentrations of the analytes. These findings demonstrate that the method possesses high sensitivity, making it suitable for detecting trace amounts of sodium benzoate and caffeine.

Method Validation Summary

The validation parameters, including linearity, precision, accuracy, robustness, and sensitivity, confirm that the developed UV spectroscopic method is scientifically sound, precise, and reproducible. The low %RSD values, high correlation coefficient, and acceptable recovery range indicate that this method meets ICH guidelines for analytical method validation and is suitable for the quantification of sodium benzoate and caffeine in pharmaceutical formulations.

Table 4: Summary of validation parameters

parameter	Result	
	Sodium benzoate	caffeine
Lambda max (nm)	224 nm	272 nm
Range	5-30 µg/ml	5-30 µg/ml
Regression equation	$y = 0.038x + 0.348$	$y = 0.037x + 0.349$
Slope	0.038	0.037
Intercept	0.348	0.349
Correlation coefficient	0.998	0.998
LOD	0.3552µg/ml	0.3489 µg/ml
LOQ	1.0763 µg/ml	1.0548 µg/ml

Forced Degradation Study

The forced degradation study revealed significant degradation under various stress conditions, highlighting the susceptibility of sodium benzoate and caffeine to environmental factors.

Photolytic degradation exhibited the highest degradation rates, with 98.92% for sodium benzoate and 85.34% for caffeine. This extensive breakdown is attributed to UV light absorption, photochemical reactions, reactive oxygen species (ROS) formation, and environmental exposure. These findings reinforce the importance of storing beverages and pharmaceutical formulations away from direct sunlight to ensure stability.

Oxidative degradation resulted in 87.44% degradation for sodium benzoate and 21.84% for caffeine, likely due to oxidative stress induced by hydroxyl radicals, which trigger demethylation, ring cleavage, and conversion into smaller oxidized products.

Acid degradation led to 58.52% degradation in sodium benzoate and 36.91% in caffeine. Caffeine undergoes protonation, demethylation, and ring cleavage, forming smaller nitrogenous compounds. Sodium benzoate, on the other hand, transforms into benzoic acid, which subsequently undergoes hydroxylation and oxidation, leading to ring cleavage and CO₂ formation.

Alkaline degradation was observed at 46.71% for sodium benzoate and 32.87% for caffeine. In alkaline conditions, caffeine degrades due to nucleophilic hydroxide attack, resulting in demethylation and ring opening. While sodium benzoate is relatively stable under mild alkaline conditions, strong alkalinity induces hydroxylation and oxidative cleavage of the benzene ring, leading to degradation.

Thermal degradation accounted for 40.33% degradation in sodium benzoate and 33.76% in caffeine. Caffeine undergoes thermal sublimation, demethylation, oxidation, and ring cleavage, while sodium benzoate undergoes thermal decarboxylation, forming benzene, which further oxidizes at higher temperatures.

These findings underscore the necessity of controlled storage conditions to preserve the stability and efficacy of sodium benzoate and caffeine in pharmaceutical and food formulations. Results are summarised in figure 4 and figure 5

Fig 4: Graphical representation of Sodium benzoate forced degradation

Fig 5: graphical representation of caffeine forced degradation study

Analysis of sample showed that the highest concentration of Sodium benzoate was found in sample MD (8.8184 μ g/ml&6.2881 μ g/ml by technique1&technique2 respectively) and lowest concentration in sample STN(5.7062 μ g/ml&6.1573 μ g/ml by technique1&technique2 respectively). The concentration of Sodium benzoate in carbonated drinks (MD,PRD,STN,CG) ranged between 5.7062 μ g/ml to5.7062 μ g/ml in technique1 and between 6.1573 μ g/ml to 6.1573 μ g/ml in technique 2.Analysis of sample showed that the highest concentration of Caffeine was found in sample PRD (30.6262 μ g/ml &30.6138 μ g/ml by technique1 & technique2 respectively)and lowest concentration in sample MD(27.6953 μ g/ml& 29.835 μ g/ml by technique1&technique2 respectively). The concentration of Caffeine in carbonated drinks (MD,PRD,STN,CG) ranged between 27.6953 μ g/ml to30.6262 μ g/ml in technique1 and between 29.835 μ g/ml to 30.6138 μ g/ml in technique 2.Results are summarised in figure 6 and figure 9

Fig 6: Sample analysis of Caffeine (Technique 1)

Fig 7: Sample analysis of Caffeine (Technique 2)

Fig 8: Sample analysis of sodium Benzoate (Technique 1)

Fig 9: Sample analysis of sodium Benzoate (Technique 2)

5.SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

A simple, convenient, and cheaper spectrophotometric method has been developed and validated to quantify sodium benzoate & caffeine levels in various brand of marketed carbonated drinks product using UV-Visible Spectrophotometer.

As per ICH guidelines, the analytical method used for determination of sodium benzoate & caffeine content was validated and was found showing Linearity, specificity, Robustness, precision and stability when compared with previously reported study. Moreover forced degradation studies were carried out on developed method on different stress condition. Hence this method can be successfully used to detect and quantify the presence of sodium benzoate & caffeine in food product.

In this work we carried out and found sodium benzoate & caffeine in variable amount in different carbonated drinks. The estimated sodium benzoate & caffeine exposure levels from the consumption of these products were shown to be within FDA approved limit, which is about 0.1 % by weight for sodium benzoate and for caffeine 145 mg/L & not more than 300 mg/L.

Analysis of commercial soft drinks showed varying concentrations of sodium benzoate and caffeine, with the highest caffeine concentration in sample PRD and the highest sodium benzoate concentration in sample MD. These results highlight the necessity for stringent quality control to ensure compliance with regulatory standards.

In conclusion, the validated UV-spectrophotometric method provides an effective, accurate, and reliable approach for quantifying sodium benzoate and caffeine in beverages. The forced

degradation findings emphasize the importance of controlled storage conditions to maintain product stability and safety

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